

Table 1. Average yield data and yield characteristics of promising scented cultures. Gujarat, India, 1980-83.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Flowering (d)	Plant height (cm)	1000-grain weight (g)	Length (mm)	Breadth (mm)	Classification	Milled rice recovery (%)
GR101	4.1	105	101	19.3	9.52	2.24	Fine	69.63
Pankhali 203 (check)	2.2	92	140	17.2	8.43	2.30	Fine	53.78

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Table 2. Quality characteristics of GR101.

Variety	Kernel		Water uptake (%)	Alkali spreading	Alkali clearing	Protein (%)	Moisture (%)	Starch value	After cooking			Taste
	Length (mm)	Breadth (mm)							Appearance	Cohesiveness	Tenderness	
GR101	6.5	1.9	295	Completely dispersed	Collar cleared	7	13	21	Whole smooth grain	Well-separated grain	Firm and chewy	Scented
Pankhali 203 (check)	5.7	1.9	185	Collar incomplete	Collar cottony	7	13	6	Indistinct broken grain	Sticky	Firm and chewy	Scented

Physicochemical properties as a basis for identifying preferred cooking quality

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Many physicochemical properties

influence the cooking quality of milled rice. We measured physicochemical parameters of 40 popular rice varieties (Table 1). The varieties were classified as rices with high, medium, and low cooking quality on the basis of total points (Table 2).

Table 1. Cooking quality of physicochemical characteristics of milled rice. Coimbatore, India.

Characteristic	Cooking quality		
	High	Medium	Low
Pericarp	Red	White	-
Single grain weight (mg)	>23	18.0 -22.9	<18
Length (mm)	<5	5.0 - 5.99	>6
Shape L/B/T ^a	<1.2	1.21- 1.59	>1.6
Surface area (cm ² /g)	<15.0	15.1 -16.9	>17.0
Alkali disintegration value	>6.0	3.1 - 5.99	<3.0
Cooked volume for 100 g rice (CC)	<260	261-279	>280
Elongation ratio in length	<1.4	1.40- 1.59	>1.6
Elongation ratio in shape (L/B)	<2.4	2.41- 2.99	>3.0
Amylose content (%)	<20.00	20.00-24.99	>25

^a Length-breadth-thickness.

Table 2. Total evaluation points of rice varieties and cultures. ^a Coimbatore, India.

Variety or culture	Total
IR20	28
Ponni	28
IR60	28
Bhavani	27
IR50	27
CO41	27
White Ponni	27
ADT36	27
IR62	26
CO 44	26
IR42	25
NLR	25
CO 37	23
ADT27	23
CO 43	23
CO 25	23
ASD15	22
Ponmani	21
IR8	17
TKM9	17
ASD1	16
ASD7	15
TNAU801790	28
TNAU831293	26
TNAU801793	26
AD85001	26
TNAU80042	25
TNAU80058	25
AS25370	25
TNAU80030	23
AD9408	23
AS13744	21
BS8	20
IET7301	20
IET7590	20
AS28883	20
IET7303	20
BC367-4	20
TM8089	19

^aHigh = >25, medium = 20-24, low = <20.

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